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Analysis of Advertising Effectiveness on Television Using the Epic Model

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Abstract

As a condition that occurs continuously in the course of life, the trading system has evolved in such a way that it has reached the digital trading system practiced by today's society. Over time, advertising in digital media is considered more effective than mainstream media such as television advertisements. Supported by statistical data collection techniques that make it easier for the audience to detect and display social media ads, or can directly target potential buyers who have conducted similar searches in the past. However, several facts still show that TV advertising is still the top choice by brands and has the highest percentage of ad spending compared to other advertisements. This quantitative study took primary data through questionnaires and the results of the data were processed using SPSS 25 to test the effectiveness of TV advertising with non-parametric tests and ANOVA tests.

Keywords: *Effectiveness, Television Media, EPIC Model*

Abstrak

Sebagai suatu kondisi yang terjadi terus menerus dalam keberlangsungan hidup, sistem perdagangan telah berevolusi sedemikian rupa hingga mencapai sistem perdagangan digital yang dilakukan masyarakat saat ini. Seiring berjalannya waktu, beriklan di media digital dinilai lebih efektif dibandingkan dengan media mainstream seperti iklan televisi. Didukung dengan teknik pengumpulan data statistik yang memudahkan pendeteksian dan tampilan iklan media sosial oleh audiens, atau bisa langsung menysasar pada calon pembeli yang pernah melakukan pencarian serupa di masa lalu. Namun, beberapa fakta masih menunjukkan bahwa iklan TV masih menjadi pilihan utama oleh merek dan memiliki persentase belanja iklan tertinggi dibandingkan iklan lainnya. Penelitian kuantitatif ini mengambil data primer melalui kuesioner dan hasil data diolah menggunakan SPSS 25 untuk menguji efektivitas iklan TV dengan uji non-parametrik dan uji Anova.

Kata Kunci: *Efektivitas, Media Televisi, EPIC Model*

INTRODUCTION

As for some previous studies related to this title. First, research that focuses on the definition of the concept of advertising, according to Putra & Sudrajat (2019), advertising is a form of commercial and non-personal communication about an organization and its products that is transmitted to a target audience through mass media such as television, radio, newspapers, magazines, direct mail, outdoor billboards, or public vehicles. Second, according to Hariyadi & Luthfie (2019) advertising is one of the four important items used by companies to launch persuasive communication to targeted buyers and the public. Basically, advertising is a form of communication to fulfill the marketing function. Third (Asari, 2021) in (Hermawan, 2012) advertising is a presentation and promotion of ideas, goods or services carried out by a particular company. The main key to advertising is that an advertisement must be able to get the attention of potential customers to the product or service being offered.

Furthermore, researchers who focus on the effectiveness of advertising. First, according to (Kawahara, 2021) advertising can be effective if it is well directed and integrated with other elements, an advertisement must look at the consumer's point of view, then at the potential consumer's perception of an advertisement, which advertisements with high originality, closeness to good consumers or influence consumers to want to know a product will be advertisements that are always remembered by consumers. Second, according to (Pancaningrum & Sari, 2019) in (Effendy, 2005) advertising effectiveness is also how far the message conveyed can attract, be understood, understood and can move consumers to respond to the advertisement. The effectiveness of advertising can be measured by how much impact the communication conveyed through advertising has on consumer awareness and knowledge. A company uses television as an advertising medium because television is a medium that combines audio, visual and motion. Third, there is also research from (Tafesse & Wood, 2021) which states that advertising can be done through the content of influencers on Instagram to reach public attention. This method utilizes the credibility possessed by influencers and the trust their followers have in the advertising information conveyed by influencers and indicates that advertising is done to be sought after by potential customers.

Furthermore, research that discusses the impact of advertising faced by consumers, according to (Baskoro, 2021) advertising does not directly impact the purchase of a product but remains an effective marketing tool in establishing communication between companies and consumers and as an effort to deal with competitors. For most companies, advertising is an attractive option, apart from being a source of information, advertising is also seen as an entertainment medium and an effective marketing communication medium to reach the target market, especially if it is broadcast on television.

Furthermore, research aimed at calculating the EPIC model (Baskoro, 2021) The overall results of the survey using the EPIC method on the effectiveness of advertisements on the community from each dimension, television advertisements have a good ability to get the attention of the audience, especially residents of East Jakarta. This shows that print advertising is still getting attention. (Azis & Nurfebriaraning, 2021) stated that the advertisement he researched using the EPIC model was very effective because the respondents he was targeting, namely Telkom University students, had succeeded in involving consumers by creating an emotional closeness and getting a positive response based on the respondents' assessment where the respondents became interested and interested and even intended to use it.

Basic Theory

The basic theory that researchers use in this study is, according to (Irianto, 2007) a population data will be normally distributed if the average value is the same as the mode, median, and also some values that collect their position in the middle and continued by analyzing the EPIC Model, this analysis is carried out by calculating the range of effectiveness scales as a reference for assessing each dimension of the EPIC model.

Objective

This study aims to determine the level of effectiveness of So Nice Sausage advertisements that have been carried out by previous researchers, advertising is Laskey et al (in (Nur & Bambang, 2013)) stated that the effectiveness of an advertisement depends on whether consumers remember the message conveyed, understand the message, are influenced by the message and of course ultimately buy the advertised product. The results of this study can be used as a reference and input for students, and the public in understanding advertisements in television media.

METHOD

This research uses Quantitative methods with descriptive research techniques using survey methods. Then complemented by using appropriate methods, which are document analysis, and questionnaires. The structured questionnaire is given to respondents and is designed to produce specific information. Then calculated based on SPSS with the correct scale and calculation.

Descriptive Analysis by EPIC Model Method

Advertising effectiveness can be measured using the EPIC model analysis, which uses a Likert scale to measure advertising effectiveness on each dimension. For respondents, it is used to determine the level of effectiveness and ineffectiveness of statements about people, objects, behaviors, etc. The results of the measurement are then forwarded to the respondent so that it can trigger a response for each response with a different value. The measurement results are then forwarded to respondents so that they can trigger a response for each response with a different value. Ad performance can be determined using simple table analysis, weighted average calculation, EPIC index, and standard deviation.

Tabulated Data Analysis

For the formula method used according to (Sukmadinata, 2012), namely:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rentang skor} &= \frac{\text{nilai skor tertinggi} - \text{nilai skor terendah}}{\text{jumlah kategori}} \\ &= \frac{5 - 1}{5} = 0,8 \end{aligned}$$

Where the highest score value = 5 and the lowest score value = 1

In each dimension of the EPIC Model separately, it will be analyzed using the average score method to determine whether the effectiveness of each dimension, then the average value will be included in the scale range from very ineffective (STE) to very effective scale range (SE).

Dengan demikian posisi keputusan menjadi:

	STE	TE	CE	E	SE
	1,00	1,80	2,60	3,40	4,20
5,00					

Keterangan :

STE	= Sangat Tidak Efektif	(masuk skala 1,00 – 1,80)
TE	= Tidak Efektif	(masuk skala 1,81 – 2,60)
CE	= Cukup Efektif	(masuk skala 2,61 – 3,40)
E	= Efektif	(masuk skala 3,41 – 4,20)
SE	= Sangat Efektif	(masuk skala 4,21 – 5,00)

Analysis of the EPIC Model Approach

(Duriyanto et al., 2003)) revealed that the impact of communication caused by an advertisement can be analyzed, one of which is by using the EPIC Model. The dimensions in the EPIC Model are analyzed separately using the average score method to determine the effectiveness of each dimension. Later the average value will determine the position of an ad's effectiveness (Prakoso & Rofiq, 2016), according to the results of the epic model in the table.

Hasil Epic Model					
No.	Dimensi	Iklan TV		Iklan Retargeting	
		Rata - Rata	Ket	Rata - Rata	Ket
1	<i>Empathy</i>	2,45	TE	2,62	E
2	<i>Persuasion</i>	2,35	TE	2,60	E
3	<i>Impact</i>	2,89	E	2,93	E
4	<i>Communica-tion</i>	2,83	E	2,84	E
Rata - Rata		2,63	E	2,75	E

Sumber: Hasil Olah Data 2020

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

It is known from the data of advertising management results that there are 50 descriptive respondents consisting of 23 men and 27 women. Most respondents are under 30 years old, as many as 33 people and 17 people over 30 years old. Based on the level of employment, the most respondents are other jobs 26 people, students or students 24 people, and the highest income is 1,000,000 and the lowest is 500,000. -1.000.000.

Analyzing the Epic Model Approach

In this study, the reliability test used the Cronbach's Alpha method (Uyanto, 2009) where a questionnaire is said to be reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value is > 0.600 because decision making in this method uses the 0.600 limit as the r table (Triton, 2007).

Indikator	r Hitung	r Tabel	Keterangan
Menyukai Iklan	0,625	0,361	Valid
Ketertarikan	0,751	0,361	Valid
Keinginan Membeli Produk	0,588	0,361	Valid
Pengetahuan tentang suatu produk	0,473	0,361	Valid
kretifitas iklan	0,669	0,361	Valid
Kejelasan Informasi Iklan	0,474	0,361	Valid
Penyampaian Iklan	0,596	0,361	Valid
Pemahaman Konsumen terhadap iklan	0,579	0,361	Valid

ANOVA Test

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19994.933	2	9997.466	32.701	.000 ^b
	Residual	3668.667	12	305.722		
	Total	23663.600	14			

a. Dependent Variable: Sales

b. Predictors: (Constant), Discounts, Promotions

Table 2.1

Third Part Output (ANOVA): From the output, it is known that the value of F count = 32,701 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. then the regression model can be used to predict the Sales variable or in other words, there is an influence of the Promotion (X1) and discount (X2) variables on the Sales (Y) variable.

Empathy Table 2.2

Report
Model

Empathy	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
3	2.00	2	.000
4	2.00	2	.000
5	2.00	3	.000
6	2.00	5	.000
7	2.00	6	.000
8	2.00	4	.000
9	2.00	3	.000
Total	2.00	25	.000

Persuasion Table 2.3

Report
Model

Persuasion	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
4	2.00	1	.
5	2.00	2	.000
6	2.00	3	.000
7	2.00	8	.000
8	2.00	5	.000
9	2.00	4	.000
10	2.00	1	.
11	2.00	1	.
Total	2.00	25	.000

Impact Table 2.4

Report
Model

Impact	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
3	2.00	2	.000
4	2.00	3	.000
5	2.00	3	.000
6	2.00	3	.000
7	2.00	7	.000
8	2.00	3	.000
9	2.00	3	.000
10	2.00	1	.
Total	2.00	25	.000

Communication Tabel 2.5

Report
Model

Communication	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
4	2.00	1	.
5	2.00	4	.000
6	2.00	9	.000
7	2.00	2	.000
8	2.00	4	.000
9	2.00	2	.000
10	2.00	3	.000
Total	2.00	25	.000

From the four tables above, it has proven that advertising on TV has a significant difference for the EPIC Model method. But it has effective results.

Discussion

The results of the analysis support five hypotheses, namely that advertising messages have a positive effect on brand recognition, advertising messages and brand recognition have a positive effect on consumer confidence, advertising messages and brand recognition have an effect on consumer attitudes, consumer confidence and consumer attitudes have a positive effect on purchase intentions, and purchase intentions have a positive effect on purchases. The importance of an advertisement or communication is related to its function, which is to state and provide information to the audience about the overall description of a product used.

CONCLUSION

Advertising media is a means of communication used to disseminate advertising messages. Knowing what consumers are looking for is considered important by producers. As a living being, every individual has an obligation to carry out their daily interests and requires various kinds of goods to fulfill basic and secondary needs.

No matter how good the quality of a product is if it is not followed by the existence of the product in the market (market), then there is little chance for the product to be purchased and consumed by consumers. With perfect information that consumers have about the state of the market and the products in it, it will affect the level of competition in the market, and conversely, limited information about the conditions (price, quality, etc.) of products in the market causes each producer to have a demand curve that shows a negative slope that can cause market power for each producer.

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